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PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS PRESENTED IN IRIS MURDOCH'S NOVEL “THE SANDCASTLE”

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ABSTRACT

Iris Murdoch is a prolific writer of 20th century English literature. She is a renowned author of many significant works that contain philosophical thoughts. In this article, we analyze her third novel “The Sandcastle” which was published in 1957. In contemporary English literature, the leading philosophical tendency was clearly Existentialism that founded by Jean Paul Sartre. Though, throughout her career Murdoch had dynamically dimensional philosophical views, and Existentialism was her first interest that led her to create novels with philosophical coating. Iris Murdoch literally accepted a clear way of the philosophy, which Sartre investigated. The purpose of this article is to define philosophical peculiarities of the novel “The Sandcastle”. In this novel, the author shows the inexhaustibility of humankind, the unguessed actions of the characters, the notions such as coincides of art and truth, freedom, and morality.

Keywords: philosophy, existentialism, love, morality, art, truth, family, fidelity, reality, freedom, ego

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Айрис Мердок является автором многочисленных работ английской литературы 20-го века. Она написала много значительных работ, содержащие философские мысли. В данной статье мы анализируем ее третий роман «Замок на песке», опубликованный в 1957 году. Ведущим философским течением в современной английской литературе без спору был экзистенциализм, основанный Жаном Полем Сартром. Все же, на протяжении всей своей карьеры у Мердока были динамичные философские взгляды, и экзистенциализм был ее первым интересом, который привел ее к созданию романов с философской оболочкой. Айрис Мердок буквально восприняла ясный путь философии, которую исследовал Сартр. Цель данной статьи - определить философские особенности романа «Замок на песке». В этом романе автор показывает неисчерпаемость человечества, непредвиденность поступков героев, такие понятия, как пересечение искусства и правды, свободы и нравственности.

Ключевые слова: философия, экзистенциализм, любовь, нравственность, искусство, истина, семья, верность, реальность, свобода, эгоизм

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AYRIS MURDOKNING “QUMQASR” ROMANIDA TAQDIM ETILGAN FALSAFIY ASPEKTLAR

ANNOTATSIYA

Ayris Myordak 20-asr ingliz adabiyotining sermahsul yozuvchisi hisoblanadi. U falsafiy fikrlarni o'z ichiga olgan ko'plab ahamiyatli asarlarning taniqli muallifi. Ushbu maqolada biz uning 1957-yilda nashr etilgan "Qum qal'a" nomli uchinchi romanini tahlil qilamiz. Zamonaviy ingliz adabiyotida asosiy falsafiy tendentsiya Jan Pol Sartr asos solgan ekzistensializm deb bilinadi. O'z faoliyati davomida Myordak turli falsafiy qarashlar egasi bo'lgan va ekzistensializm falsafasi uning e'tiboriga uchragan birinchi tendentsiya bo'lib, muallifning falsafiy qarashlarini o'zida aks etgan romanlarning vujudga kelishiga turtki bo'lgan. Ayris Myordak Sartr o'rgangan falsafaning aniq yo'lini tom ma'noda qabul qildi. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi "Qum qal'a" romanining falsafiy o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini aniqlashdir. Muallif bu romanda insoniyatning abadiyligini, qahramonlarning tahmin qilib bo'lmaydigan xatti-harakatlarini, san'at va haqiqat, erkinlik va axloq kabi tushunchalarning kesishishini ko'rsatib o'tadi.

Kalit so'zlar: falsafa, ekzistensializm, sevgi, axloq, san'at, haqiqat, oila, vafo, voqe'lik, erkinlik, egoizm

Contemporary English literature is rich in renowned writers, who contributed to developing literature, saving it from dying and losing its color, emotiveness, and expressiveness. One of the flamboyant writers in the English literature of the XX century was Iris Murdoch. Iris Murdoch (1919-1999) is considered to be a founder of the contemporary English novel with philosophical inclination, whose works are deep, mysterious, and magic. She was born in 1919, Dublin, in a family of English and Ireland descent. She studied philosophy at the Universities of Cambridge and Oxford. Additionally, for a long time, she was a lecturer at Oxford University. She expressed her philosophical theories including existentialistic views through her works. Her novels written in 1950s closely linked with Sartre's philosophy. She noted in her study "It is no superficial or perverse dilemma into which this thinker has got himself. Being a French intellectual of his time with unique views on life, Jean Paul Sartre strongly admired individual free choice and believed in social democracy, and human solitude. Following other authorities, their ideas, and way of living means for Sartre to be in a bad faith, so people need to accept their freedom, and loneliness in making life decisions. This is the way of Existentialism founded by Sartre, which declares *existence precedes essence*. This slogan denotes that each individual is responsible for shaping his/her own essence. This belief is a key feature of all Sartre's works of fiction and non-fiction. Nevertheless, Sartre using his philosophical views couldn't build this system of reality. He remained an atheist, and had no faith in God, nor in Nature; he always tried to follow logical thinking. Murdoch's position clearly can be seen in her study "Sartre – Romantic Rationalist (1953). Iris Murdoch stated, "Sartre is profoundly and self-consciously contemporary; he has the style of the age". Sartre's investigation of literature from Murdoch's point of view was the case that true literary work that can show human nature can't be created just by abstract formation. Despite his efforts, Sartre didn't see the main purpose of the literary prose – "the creation of whole, not partitioned image." Murdoch called his rationalism romantic, isolated from the sphere of the real application. Sartre could penetrate into the psychology of lonely individuum, and his analysis conduces self-awareness, but he can't lead the actions of his main heroes, therefore can't show the true way of living. Already in this book Murdoch formulated her viewpoint toward contemporary literature and the main objective of the novelist – creating plethoric human nature. A few years later Murdoch compared a novel with "an upbuilt house, in which the characters live

liberally". This metaphor explains the creativeness of Iris Murdoch, that the heroes of her novel evolve without the interaction of the author. Inasmuch as the characters are not developed under the bondage of the writer's disposition. Thus, Murdoch created novels that are not typical, additionally with dimensional characters, shreds of evidence, compositions, and images.

Starting with the novel "The Sandcastle" Murdoch presents a new theme in her fiction, the theme of art which tractates that fictional truth coincides with reality. It highlights the objectivity of the truth in a fictional world, that don't follow the author's wishes. Genuine art is defined as the ability to depict an object, not as a symbol of one's own moods, but as it is. Nevertheless, in the literary structures of her novels written at the end of the 50^s and at the beginning of the 60^s, Murdoch wasn't able to embody the realization of such art. In contrast to the rationalist views on a person, she emphasizes her mysteriousness through the unexpectedness of her behavior. The portrayal of a diverse human personality solely through unexpectedness for actions prevents the character's credibility. One of the heroines of the novel "The Sandcastle" comes to understand that the uniqueness of each person is determined by his/her "unique life story". But this story itself remains outside the scope of the narrative, and the dissimilarity of the characters doesn't stand by their life circumstances.

The third masterpiece that was written by Iris Murdoch, "The Sandcastle" tells a story of a middle-aged man, who suffers from bonding family responsibilities that lack him to make free choices. Bill Mor is married for twenty years to Nan, and has two children, Felicity and Don, with whom he struggles to find normal prospection. Bill works as a schoolmaster and has quite boring, always the same schedule. He is a man who is lack of own decisions, who is often manipulated by his wife, even though he has thirsty for changes, some kind of new adventures. And the author gives him such an opportunity by creating a compelling, romantic, and yet full of hard decisions plot. One of the similarities of Murdoch's works is having an outsider character, who tries to intimate with enchanted like community but always faces failure in his/her attempt. In "The Sandcastle" it is a mysteriously appealing young artist, Rein Carter, with whom Bill Mor falls in love and with this fragile opportunity tries to change his life by leaving his family, children, and friends. "The Art, says Murdoch in "On God and Good" has got a function to console human being in their fantasies, especially for those who want to escape from bitter reality, at the same time people try to oppose it with the more perfect reality." Bill Mor is a character who desires to vanish in his magical imagination of true love which is only a bunch of illusion. The author tries to show in this novel how one can be healthy in a moral way. Murdoch put a motif of the moral philosophy in her work, and suggested that the task of the moral philosophy is to beat "the fat relentless ego". Freedom from the self, from your ego, and awareness of others is a key point of the novel, is the only way to freedom. What would you choose love or morality, romantic freedom, or the concept of good? Moral philosophy shows a realistic picture of humankind and recommends a more perfect yet realistic one. Iris Murdoch created a moral story with enthusiasm and passion. The outsider in the novel, Rein Carter may be the most romantic egoist in Murdoch's works, the kind of a character that draws others into her abyss. She is attractive, rich, independent, and free. These features of her are the points that appeal to Bill mostly, and the enchanted one is not only him in this small community. The Headmaster Demoyte whose portrait Rain comes to paint, The teacher of art -Bledyard, and others like Mister Evvy are also seem to have some feelings toward Miss Rain Carter, though they never dare to show it explicitly.

"Vision and Choice in Morality" is Murdoch's non-fiction work that was published in 1956. She states that the moral attitudes of individuals may be different and within emphasizes the boundless complexity of the universe, the coincidence of abstract and empirical, the uniqueness of the individual, and being aware of it. On the contrary, we have our moral rules which have been brought to the perfect form, shaped through ages, and accepted by all. She establishes clear parallels between this sort of moral attitude and the artist's goal. The art, Murdoch declares, embraces all concerns of human being, and the novel genre mostly argues about the meaning of life, the existence of the individual." The reader response may be quite different after reading the novel. The author used a very extraordinary style that may easily confuse the criticism of the reader. The choices that Bill Mor has to take are neither good nor bad. Is it better to choose a new chance to live more

adventurous life, or should he stay with his family: “there would be a new life and a new world. But that which he was about to break would never mend, and he now knew he would never cease to feel the pain of it”.

Murdoch stated in her interview, “The way an author interacts with his fictional characters tells us a lot about his moral beliefs.” In “The Sandcastle”, Iris Murdoch utilized a great tactic in choosing the protagonist and the antagonist of the story. The reader always cheers up the main hero of the novel, and tries to stand with him, because it tells mostly about his feelings, his inner world, and emotions, while we can’t penetrate into the other characters’ brains. What if, the story would be told from Mor’s wife - Nan’s point of view? In that case, maybe readers would feel more sympathy toward Nan, and the role of antagonist would be given to Mor.

The dilemma of moral attitude may be explained by a Hegelian theory which Murdoch investigated in her work, “The Sublime and the Good”. She noted that the conflict between two goods, not contrast as good and evil, but specially between two virtues because both sides have approval to his/her action that materialized through dimensional social orders and beliefs, may be inevitable after challenging the tragedy.” Iris Murdoch only once shows the inner feelings expressed by Nan, which can totally change the criticism of a reader. “As she stood there Nan felt, for the first time since she had found out that something was wrong, overwhelmed with sheer misery. She had felt amazement, fury, and extreme disquiet, she had even experienced a curious exhilaration, something of the instinct of the hunter. But it had not occurred to her to feel exactly unhappy. She had never in her life allowed Bill to cause her real unhappiness. There had been, there could be, no occasion for this. In her situation, that of a successfully married woman, unhappiness of that sort would have been merely neurotic. Nan despised the neurotic. But now she felt real grief- which her husband had caused. Gradually the conception that he was interested in another woman began to reach not only her mind but her emotions. As she stood there, her back against the fence, chilled and soaked by the rain, she felt that she had suddenly been dragged into some awful nightmare: she had been driven out of her own house. Her hand went to her mouth. She shook with the grief and the horror of it. The hot tears warmed her cheek, mingling with the rain. After this evidence when Nan caught her husband with Rain Carter in her own home, the author put us an awareness that every individual tries to seek consolation from bitter reality in his/her fantasies. Tim Burke is a second character, a close friend to Bill Mor who has old and deep feelings for Nan. At the same time, Nan is also aware of this sympathy toward her but thinks it is an absurd and immoral relationship to happen, and when she feels desperately alone, she is not against embracing these warm feelings, at least to find some courage. “A curious light was shining. Nan looked up and saw directly above her a rainbow displayed against a pewter-coloured sky. She shuddered, and went back through the door which Tim Burke was holding open for her. In this small fragment, the author used symbolism with ingenuity. The display of the rainbow in this situation means the type of happiness and love that is opposite the moral rules, and we can clearly see that Nan confronts this happiness with a strong will. In the end Nan understands that the prosperity of her family is the first important thing in her life, even though her husband caused her to feel much suffering and grief. “A minute later she heard the front door close behind him. Nan waited another minute, and then she got up, went into the kitchen, and was extremely sick.”

As we mentioned above the moral philosophy teaches us a better, more moral life. Murdoch to express her philosophical views often created a side character, who often stands far from story development, and who is totally different from others, who have very complex thoughts. For this role, Murdoch in “The Sandcastle” chose Bledyard, the art teacher who often remains teased by pupils, because of his unusual lecture conducting, and stammer. However, this character stays extremely wise during the narration. He embodies the true philosopher, who knows what is right and what is wrong, and what bad consequences may cause some thoughtless actions. “That is not true, Mr. Mor,” said Bledyard. He leaned forward, stooping over Mor, his long hair flapping. “There is such a thing as respect for reality. You are living on dreams now, dreams of happiness, dreams of freedom. But in all this you consider only yourself. You do not truly apprehend the distinct being of either your wife or Miss Carter.” Bledyard has his own feelings toward Rain, nevertheless, he tries to follow not his heart but reason. At the same time, he wants to keep safe ones (Rain Carter) whom he really cares

about. Because careless actions may bring more agonizing grief than living without love. “You speak as if this were a sort of virtue,” said Bledyard, “you speak as if to be a free man was just to get what you want regardless of convention. But real freedom is a total absence of concern about yourself.” Bledyard was speaking earnestly and quickly and was now scarcely stammering at all.”

Iris Murdoch challenges the main hero of the novel with irony. In one of his lectures, Bill More says, - “Freedom is not exactly what I would call a virtue. Freedom might be called a benefit or a sort of grace, though of course to seek it or to gain it might be a proof of ment... If by freedom we mean absence of external restraint, then we may call a man lucky for being free - but why should we call him good?” Bill Mor later experience all of his words “in practice”. However, till the end, he stands hesitant and cannot simply tear up all the relationships he has built with his family and friends. With family, he built a castle of stone compared with the sandcastle. “Yes,” said Miss Carter, “but a melancholy sea as I remember it. A tideless sea. I can recall, as a child, seeing pictures in English children’s books of boys and girls playing on the sand and making sandcastles — and I tried to play on my sand. But a Mediterranean beach is not a place for playing on. It is dirty and very dry. The tides never wash the sand or make it firm. When I tried to make a sandcastle, the sand would just run away between my fingers. It was too dry to hold together. And even if I poured sea water over it, the sun would dry it up at once.”

To conclude, we need to highlight that the novel “The Sandcastle” by Iris Murdoch leaves us in dilemma. It forces us to think about life and love; awakes our muses and desire for freedom and art. At the same time, it faces us with moral rules that can’t be resisted. It teaches us to kill our ego, to care about others, and to gain real happiness. The title itself represents our wildest fantasies that may hurt the people who are close to us; the sandcastle that can be destroyed easily or even impossible to build.

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